

THE MAIN WAYS TO DEVELOP INNOVATION AND DIGITALIZATION OF AGRICULTURE IN THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN

I.E.Qalbaeva

1st year master's student of the
Faculty of Economics of Karakalpak State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15654167>

Abstract. This article substantiates the need and prerequisites for the development of innovation and digitalization of agriculture in the regions of Uzbekistan, provides an overview of government documents regulating and coordinating the development of this sphere, summarizes the results of a sociological survey on monitoring the impact of the results of implemented innovations, provides a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of innovation activity, analyzes the reasons for the low level of innovative development in agriculture, the main directions of development innovation and digitalization of agriculture in Uzbekistan are also given.

Keywords: innovation, innovative activity, innovative activity, innovative products, digitalization, agriculture, agricultural subjects.

Аннотация. В данной статье обосновывается необходимость и предпосылки развития инновации и цифровизации сельского хозяйства в регионах Узбекистана, дается обзор правительственных документов, регулирующие и координирующие развитие данной сферы, обобщены результаты социологического опроса по мониторингу влияния результатов внедренных инноваций, дается сопоставительный анализ показателей эффективности инновационной активности, анализируются причины низкого уровня инновационного развития в сельском хозяйстве, а также приводятся основные направления развития инновации и цифровизации сельского хозяйства в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: инновация, инновационная деятельность, инновационная активность, инновационная продукция, цифровизация, сельское хозяйство, сельскохозяйственные субъекты.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston hududlarida qishloq xo'jaligida innovatsiya va raqamlashtirishni rivojlantirish zarurati va shart-sharoitlari asoslangan, ushbu sohani rivojlantirishni tartibga soluvchi va muvofiqlashtiruvchi hukumat hujjatlari sharhi keltirilgan, joriy etilgan innovatsiyalar natijalarining ta'siri monitoringi bo'yicha o'tkazilgan sotsiologik so'rov natijalari umumlashtirilgan, innovatsion faoliyat samaradorligi ko'rsatkichlarining qiyosiy tahlili berilgan, qishloq xo'jaligida innovatsion

rivojlanish darajasining pastligi sabablari tahlil qilingan, shuningdek, O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligida innovatsiya va raqamlashtirishni rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari keltirilgan.

Tayanch iboralar: innovatsiya, innovatsion faoliyat, innovatsion faollik, innovatsion mahsulot, raqamlashtirish, qishloq xo'jaligi, qishloq xo'jaligi subyektlari.

In the current context of large-scale reforms being carried out to decentralize governance in the regions of our country, the role of regions is becoming increasingly important, as reforms are being implemented at the republican, regional, and other administrative-territorial units of regions, which differ significantly from each other in their natural-ecological, socio-economic, demographic, and other development parameters. In this regard, during the reform process, the Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 [1], adapted to modern conditions, was adopted, which set the task of actively attracting foreign investments to the sectors of the economy and regions of the country through the socio-economic development of regions, districts, and cities.

In addition, the first steps have been taken in the republic to transition to an innovative economy, and the necessary conditions have been created for innovative activity. In particular, by the Decree

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

No. PF-5544 [2] defines the Strategy of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "Roadmap" for the implementation of the Strategy of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the target indicators of innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. In order to ensure the implementation of the tasks set in these documents, decisions were made on the development of innovative activities in agriculture and measures were taken to introduce innovative technologies and ideas in all branches of agriculture.

In addition, the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture [3] was adopted, which defines the priority directions for the development of agriculture until 2030, including the introduction of agro-innovative ideas, increasing labor productivity, and improving the quality of products.

At the same time, the State Program for the implementation of the Action Strategy on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Development of Science, Enlightenment and digital economy" [4], assigned to relevant ministries and agencies to ensure the

development of a program of practical measures for the widespread introduction of digital technologies in agriculture, as well as intensive technologies and innovations.

The adoption of these measures will undoubtedly raise not only agriculture, but also the economy of the regions to a high level.

Now let's analyze the innovative activity in the republic's agriculture. It should be noted that since the first years of independence, large-scale reforms have been carried out in the republic to develop agriculture.

Four years have taken a new wave under the leadership of the new President Sh. Mirziyoyev.

At the same time, the low level of creation of scientific and technical developments in the agricultural sector, the low level of private and state investments, the organization of innovative structures, and the low level of development of mechanisms for creating innovative structures, developing, and stimulating innovative activity are hindering the growth of agricultural production rates. Statistical data show that the share of the agricultural sector in the total volume of innovative goods, works, and services is only 0.7 percent. As our previous research has shown, the main problem is the lack of funds and the absence of a need for new innovative products.

In this regard, based on the study of best practices, the main focus should be on the following tasks for the innovative development of agriculture: introduction of modern technologies for storing and transporting agricultural products, including membrane technologies; creation of agro-industrial clusters in the most important areas of the agro-industrial complex, taking into account the subsequent implementation of logistics and finished natural products; providing financial assistance to agricultural producers, depending on the type and size of products they produce, with the definition of specific funding sources; implementation of effective foreign experience in automating the management of drip irrigation, organic farming, and agricultural production processes; use of geoinformation technologies in the placement of products in agriculture and water management; introduction of modern technologies for making objective decisions, collecting, storing, and processing data; organization of horticulture in closed areas and increasing its efficiency, introduction of open hydroponic technologies; application of laser planning methods to improve the melioration state of irrigated lands; introduction of new agricultural directions, taking into account the existing capabilities of the regions; ensuring food security through the development of the food industry, expanding the range of

manufactured products, including public catering; placing other crops with high economic efficiency in areas where traditional crops are sown and yields are low; creating a digital "Agriculture" platform in the regions to collect, process, and store large volumes of information generated from various sources for implementing regional innovation policy in the agricultural sector.

Bibliographic list:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. UP-4947 "On the Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan."
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 21, 2018 No. UP-5544 "On Approving the Strategy of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan."
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 No. UP-5853 "On Approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030"
4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 2, 2020 No. UP-5953 "On the State Program for the implementation of the Action Strategy on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Development of Science, Enlightenment and the Digital Economy"
5. Papaconstantinou G., Sakurai N., Wyckoff A. Embodied Technology Difusion: An Empirical Analysis for 10 OECD Countries // STI Working Papers. OECD. 1996/1. Verspagen
B. Economic growth and technological change // STI Working Papers. OECD. 2001/01. -P. 16.
6. Main indicators of scientific and technical potential and innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan: Annual statistical collection. State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018

